

the severe yellowing and stunting of the seedlings, but seedling growth was similar in Pangil peat soil, where disease incidence was greater.

The difference in disease severity may be due to the available soil nutrients that affect the plant tissues and the biochemistry of the host. Nutritional factors change the host's growing status,

cell structure, and chemical composition. The soil chemistry may affect pathogenesis, resulting in effects on disease incidence and severity. Plant nutrients required for pathogenesis are affected by the availability of soil nutrients that control plant growth and vigor and influence the plants' resistance to blast. Different varieties may respond

differently to the same nutritional environment, as demonstrated by Carreon, KTH 17, and IR442. The effect of excess or deficient essential elements in the soil on disease incidence and severity appears to depend on the combination of such elements as well as on the host and the pathogen. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Flight activities of brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, and their predator *C. lividipennis* in Malaysia

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The largest outbreak of the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* reported in Malaysia occurred in the Muda Irrigation Scheme in June 1979. It established the need for continuous surveillance of the pest. Light traps are an efficient device for monitoring the

planthoppers and some of their natural enemies. The light trap consists of a kerosene pressure lamp suspended about 1.8 m over a basin of water. Light traps were set in the Crop Protection building in Telok Chengai to study the flight activities of WBPH and the brown planthopper (BPH) and their predator *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* at half-hour intervals from 1830 to 2300 hours.

Data from catches during 13 nights were analyzed. The percentage catch for each of the three insects was

calculated (see figure). Flight activities begin after 1900 hours, when the Kedah sky darkens. The main activity for all 3 insects appears to occur from 1930 to 2000 hours. Both WBPH and BPH continue to be active until 2100 hours. *C. lividipennis* is most active from 1930 to 2000 hours. The study indicated that light traps must be lighted only from 1900 to 2200 hours to monitor the BPH and WBPH in the Muda Irrigation Scheme. ■

Catch (%)

Flight activities of the whitebacked planthopper *S. furcifera*, the brown planthopper *N. lugens*, and *Clividipennis*. Kedah, Malaysia.

Effect of depth of submergence on incidence of bacterial blight and white grub infestation in transplanted rice

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Water submergence was conducive to the spread of bacterial blight caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae*, but it effectively checked white grub infestation in transplanted IR24 in a field experiment at Pantnagar, India.

The disease incidence in the deep submergence treatment was significantly higher than that in the saturation and rainfed treatments, but similar to that in shallow submergence (see table).

White grub infestation decreased with increasing depth of submergence. Significantly fewer plants were damaged

Effect of depth of submergence on bacterial blight (BB) incidence and white grub infestation in transplanted rice, 1973 wet season. Pantnagar, India.

Treatment	BB ^a disease index	White grub damage (%)
15 cm – 1 cm	5.07	1.6
5 cm – field capacity	4.15	3.3
1 cm – field capacity	1.65	11.5
36 cm total water (50% total water use)	0.87	20.4
Rainfed	0.90	17.5
CD at 5%	1.07	5.0
CV %	28.00	30.5

^aOn 0–9 All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) scale, where 0 = no disease incidence.

in the deep and shallow submergence treatments than in the saturation and rainfed treatments. ■

Oxadiazon, a promising herbicide for dry-seeded rice in Sudan Gezira

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The semiarid Sudan Gezira has good potential for high rice production; it is rich in solar radiation and free from major pests. It has well-controlled irrigation but because of socioeconomic factors, farmers drill rice directly into dry soil and water the crop as needed until flooding commences 6 weeks after seeding. The result is severe infestation of upland weeds of the genera *Phyllanthus*, *Leucas*, *Aristolochia*, *Echinochloa*, *Solanum*, *Momordica*, *Cyperus*, *Merremia*, and *Ocimum*.

Hand weeding is tedious and costly, and herbicides have been used unsuccessfully because they have been applied without any preevaluation. The identification of effective herbicides suitable for controlling dominant weed species such as *P. niruri* and *L. urticifolia* is therefore essential.

In 1978, 11 herbicide treatments plus hand-weeded and unweeded controls were laid out in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications at the Gezira Agricultural Research Farm. The herbicides were applied at recommended rates and times. A knapsack sprayer was used to deliver about 450 liters/ha.

Effects of 11 herbicides on grain yield of the rice IR2053-206-1-3-6, and on weed density and species. Sudan Gezira, 1978.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weeds (no./m ²)	Uncontrolled weed genera (decreasing order of density)
Oxadiazon	4.34	7.7	<i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Solanum</i> .
X-150	4.03	13.7	<i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Solanum</i> , <i>Merremia</i> .
Oxyfluorfen	3.43	12.6	<i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Solanum</i> .
Pendimethalin	3.25	19.2	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Solanum</i> , <i>Leucas</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> .
Bentazon ^a	2.96	20.0	<i>Solanum</i> , <i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Leucas</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> .
Dinitramine	2.78	31.7	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Leucas</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Momordica</i> .
Thiobencarb ^a	2.46	38.7	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Ipomea</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Ocimum</i> .
Butralin	2.32	30.0	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Leucas</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> .
Propanil ^a	2.26	23.2	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Echinochloa</i> .
Diethatyl	2.25	27.5	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Solanum</i> , <i>Leucas</i> .
Piperophos-dimethametryn	2.20	11.0	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Echinochloa</i> .
Handweeded (20 + 40 DE) ^b	4.67	–	–
Unweeded	1.31	40.2	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Leucas</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Merremia</i> , <i>Momordica</i> , <i>Ipomea</i> , <i>Ocimum</i> .
S.E. ±	0.27	3.86	

^aNow used in the Gezira. ^bDays after rice emergence.

The yields of IR2053-206-1-3-6 were 72% lower in the unweeded plots than in the hand-weeded (see table). They were significantly higher in all the herbicide treatments than in the unweeded control. Oxadiazon gave the highest yield, comparable to that in the hand-weeded treatment. It effectively controlled

most of the weed flora without being phytotoxic to the rice plant. Being a preemergence herbicide, oxadiazon is preferable in the almost fully mechanized farming system of the Gezira. X-150, oxyfluorfen, and pendimethalin also were promising. ■

Egg parasites of the yellow stem borer in West Bengal

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Natural enemies play an important role in the control of populations of the rice yellow borer *Tryporyza incertulas* (Wlk.). They should be considered for maintaining homeostasis, particularly in the wet season when chemical protection is neither economical nor feasible in low-lying areas of West Bengal. Egg parasites are important components in the faunal

composition of natural enemies. Five hymenopteran insects have been noted on yellow borer egg masses at the Chinsurah Station and identified from IBP Handbook 14 as *Tetrastichus schoenobii* Ferr., *Telenomus dignus* Gahan, *Telenomus dignoides* Nixon, *Telenomus rowani* Gahan, and *Trichogramma japonicum* Ashm. The percentage of parasitism was estimated from the emergence of parasitoids from the viable eggs of field-collected egg masses (see table).

The low parasitism in March and

Egg parasitization of the yellow stem borer at Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Month	Egg masses (no.)	Sterile egg masses (no.)	Parasitized egg masses (no.)	Parasitization (%)
Feb	136	24	70	62
Mar	117	25	48	52
Apr	136	34	41	40
May	44	24	14	71
Jun	45	10	12	34
Jul	36	2	16	48
Aug	26	2	17	71
Sep	35	2	21	63
Oct	137	9	70	55
Nov	164	54	98	89